

conditions of Xiangtan. Under natural conditions, there is no pollen in the anther 15 Jul-20 Sep. We consider sunlight period to be the primary factor affecting its sterility and fertility transformation; air temperature is not important. This means it is a truly photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile rice. ■

Breeding methods— tissue culture

Embryogenic cell suspension and plant regeneration from protoplasts of indica rice

G. C. Ghosh Biswas and F. J. Zapata, Tissue Culture Laboratory, Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry, IIRRI

Cell suspension established from anther-derived callus of indica rice cultivar IR43 was used for protoplast isolation and culture.

Callus was induced following the standard anther culture technique developed at IIRRI: Anthers inoculated individually in plastic petri dishes (60 × 15 mm) containing 6 ml of SK-1 medium, and cultures incubated in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C for 1 mo.

Embryogenic calli (approximately 2 g) were selected and placed in 125-ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing 30 ml of liquid AA medium to initiate suspension cultures. The cultures were placed on a gyrotary shaker (120 rpm) in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. Liquid medium was replaced every 5-6 d. After 3-4 mo, the actively dividing embryogenic cell suspension established was maintained by weekly subculturing at 1:4 dilution (suspension inoculum: fresh medium).

To isolate protoplasts, 3- to 4-d-old cells were incubated for 4 h in a solution containing 1.0% Cellulase Onozuka RS, 0.2% Pectolyase Y-23,5 mM MES, CPW salts, and 13% mannitol at pH 5.6. The protoplasts were sieved through 45- to 25-µm nylon mesh, collected by centrifuging at 100 × g for 5 min, and washed 3 times in CPW salts containing 13% mannitol.

Protoplasts were cultured in 60- × 15-mm plastic petri dishes containing 3 ml MS1 medium at 1-2 × 10⁵ pp/ml, and maintained in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. After 3-4 wk, the agarose layer was cut into four blocks and transferred to a fresh medium without glucose but supplemented with 3.0% sucrose.

For plant regeneration, 100 calli about 4-5 mm in diameter were transferred to test tubes containing 20 ml of MSYo medium and kept under 12 h darknight photoperiod at 25 ± 1 °C.

Media compositions (SK-1, AA, MS1, MSYo) and growth substances used for different steps of the cultures are given in the table.

Media composition.

Constituent	Amount (mg/liter)			
	SK-1	AA	MS1	MSYo
KNO ₃	3,150	-	1,900	1,900
NH ₄ NO ₃	-	-	1,650	1,650
KH ₂ PO ₄	540	170	170	170
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	150	440	440	440
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	185	370	370	370
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	27.85	27.85	27.85	27.85
Na ₂ EDTA	37.25	37.25	37.25	37.25
KCl	-	2,940	0	0
KI	1.0	0.83	0.83	0.83
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	-	0.025	0.025	0.025
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
CuSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10	8.6	8.6	8.6
MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	22.3	22.3	22.3	22.3
H ₃ BO ₃	6	6.2	6.2	6.2
Inositol	100	100	100	100
Nicotinic acid	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Pyridoxine-HCl	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Thiamine-HCl	2.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
Glycine	2.0	75.0	2.0	2.0
L-glutamine	-	877	-	-
L-aspartic acid	-	266	-	-
L-arginine	-	228	-	-
Sucrose	40,000	30,000	-	30,000
Glucose	-	-	90,000	-
Casein hydrolysate	500	-	-	-
2,4-D	0.75	2.0	1.0	-
NAA	2.5	-	-	1.0
Kinetin	0.75	0.2	-	1.0
GA ₃	-	0.1	-	-
Agar	8,000	-	-	8,000
Agarose	-	-	5,000	-
PH	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8

The type of callus used (see figure, 1) was highly suitable for developing a suspension culture composed of small groups of cytoplasmic and starch-containing embryogenic cells (2). Protoplasts isolated from this suspension displayed dense cytoplasm (3).

The first division was observed after 4 d of culture (4); multicellular structures were formed after 8-10 d of culture (5). Within 3 wk of culture, most of the structure underwent further growth leading to the direct formation of recognizable globular embryoids (6). Colony formation was counted at this stage. About 0.5-0.75% plated protoplasts formed colonies. Upon transfer to

Protoplast culture and plant regeneration from indica rice. 1. Type of callus used to initiate cell suspension. 2. Cells from the embryogenic cell suspension culture. 3. Freshly isolated protoplast. 4. Dividing protoplast. 5. Multicellular structures formed from protoplasts. 6. Globular embryoid from protoplast. 7. Organized embryogenic callus obtained from protoplast-derived colonies. 8. Albino plant from protoplast-derived callus.

a fresh medium, the protocolonies continued to grow and formed white embryogenic calli with secondary embryoids on their surfaces.

Organized sectors with cup-shaped scutellar structures (7) developed in some of the protoplast-derived calli. Six percent of the transferred calli responded, producing 11 albino plants (8). ■

Yield potential

Herbage and grain yield of deepwater rices in the field

T. Kupkanchanakul, K. Kupkanchanakul, and S. Roontun, Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya 13000, Thailand; and B. S. Vergara, Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI

Some characteristics of deepwater rice—luxurious growth, poor light transmission in the canopy because of long and droopy leaves, and lodging susceptibility—can be improved by herbage removal. Deepwater rice cultivars also have traits that increase herbage production: high biomass production and very long growth duration.

Varieties may respond differently to leaf cutting. We studied the effect of leaf cutting on herbage yield, grain yield, and agronomic characteristics of deepwater rice cultivars under natural field conditions at the Huntra Rice Experiment Station in the 1989 wet season (WS). Twenty deepwater rice cultivars and two herbage treatments were evaluated. The experiment was

laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Dry seeds of deepwater rice cultivars were sown at 120 kg/ha onto plowed soil 5 May 1989. Seedlings emerged mid-May. The plants experienced drought

stress from mid-Jul to the first week of Aug.

Herbage was cut twice at the highest collar level of the last fully developed leaf—on 14 Aug (90 d after emergence [DE]) and 13 Sep (120 DE).

Table 1. Herbage and grain yield of 20 deepwater rice cultivars. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1989 WS.^a

Cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	90 DE	120 DE	Total	Control	Cut	Difference
Ban Daeng	0.6	0.5	1.0	2.2	2.4	+0.2
Huntra 60	0.8	0.6	1.4	3.1	3.2	+0.1
Khao Hoi	0.7	0.7	1.4	2.0	2.1	+0.0
Khao Kaset	0.6	0.7	1.3	2.2	2.5	+0.4
Khao Lod Chong	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.4	2.9	+0.5
Khao Mali	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.7	2.9	+0.1
Khao Praguad	0.8	0.6	1.4	2.4	2.8	+0.4
Khao Puang Nak	0.8	0.7	1.4	2.3	2.5	+0.2
Khao Rachinee	0.7	0.6	1.3	2.7	3.0	+0.4
Leb Mue Nahng 111	0.7	0.6	1.3	2.2	2.1	-0.1
Luang Pratharn	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.6	2.7	+0.1
Mali Tawng	0.9	0.8	1.6	2.5	2.6	+0.1
Nahng Khiew	0.6	0.6	1.2	2.5	2.5	+0.0
Pan Tawng	0.9	0.7	1.6	2.5	2.9	+0.4
Pin Gaew 56	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.0	2.4	+0.4
Plai Ngahm	0.6	0.6	1.2	2.4	2.7	+0.3
RD19	0.5	0.6	1.1	2.8	3.0	+0.2
Sai Bua	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.2	2.4	+0.1
Sam Ruang	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.6	2.6	+0.1
Tapow Gaew 161	0.7	0.6	1.4	1.8	2.0	+0.2
LSD 0.05	0.2	ns	ns			

^aDE = days after emergence.